

14CNIT-1372

Exergy assessment of the Spanish recovery capacity of secondary resources essential for the ecological transition

Alicia Valero^{1*}, Nicolás Villanueva¹, Jorge Torrubia¹, Paula Adánez², Virginia Rodríguez², Francisco Javier Fernández², Julio César Arranz²,

¹University of Zaragoza, Research Institute for Energy and Resource Efficiency of Aragón (Institute ENERGAIA-UNIZAR), Campus Río Ebro, Mariano Esquillor Gómez, 15, 50018, Zaragoza, Spain.

²Instituto Geológico y Minero (IGME), Departamento de Recursos Geológicos para la Transición Ecológica, Grupo de Investigación de Residuos Mineros y Geoquímica Ambiental, Ríos Rosas 23, 28003, Madrid, Spain

* aliciavd@unizar.es

1. Introduction

The increasing global demand for raw materials, driven by population growth, globalization, and shifting consumption trends, poses significant challenges to resource sustainability. The ecological transition, which seeks to replace fossil fuel dependency with renewable energy sources, will further intensify the demand for critical minerals essential for wind turbines, photovoltaic panels, and electric vehicles. This shift highlights a growing reliance on mineral resources, many of which are scarce and require substantial energy input for extraction and processing.

Exergy analysis provides a comprehensive framework for assessing the physical feasibility of raw material recovery. By quantifying the exergy replacement costs of minerals, it is possible to evaluate their physical quality, avoiding unfair comparisons. This approach allows for a more accurate representation of resource scarcity and highlights the thermodynamic limits of sustainability strategies such as circular economy initiatives and urban mining.

Urban and secondary mining have emerged as potential alternatives to conventional mining, offering opportunities to recover valuable materials from waste streams, abandoned mining sites, and discarded technological products. However, the viability of these processes depends on multiple factors, including the concentration of recoverable materials, technological feasibility, and economic considerations. Understanding these constraints is crucial for designing efficient recovery strategies and reducing dependency on primary raw materials.

This study focuses on assessing Spain's capacity for recovering secondary resources through a rigorous thermodynamic approach. By developing an inventory of materials available in mining and technological wastes, this research aims to identify feasible recovery pathways. The findings will contribute to a roadmap for optimizing raw material use, enhancing resource efficiency, and mitigating supply risks in the context of the ecological transition. Ultimately, the results will provide valuable insights into the exergy-based limitations of raw material recovery and support informed decision-making for a more sustainable resource management strategy.

2. Methodology

This study examines the recovery potential of secondary resources from both mining waste and Waste Electric and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) in Spain.

Mining Waste Assessment

A selection process was conducted to identify abandoned mining sites with high potential for resource recovery. Using data from inventories and risk assessments by IGME-CSIC over the past decade, suitability criteria were established based on economic interest, elemental concentrations relative to the Earth's crust and Spanish soils, and estimated waste volumes. As a result, three sites with significant Pb, Zn, and Ag content, a tailings pond with elevated heavy metal concentrations, and another site with high Sb and Ba levels were identified, the latter being the most promising.

Sampling campaigns were carried out at sites including Casa de la Liebre, El Soldado, Mina Claudio, Riotinto, and San Quintín. Composite surface samples were collected from each facility, with detailed sampling conducted at San Quintín up to a depth of 60 cm. Selected samples underwent optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis to determine mineral grain size, morphology, and distribution. Additional chemical analyses, including X-ray fluorescence (XRF), were performed to quantify a broader range of elements, including rare earth elements. High Sb levels at Casa de la Liebre prompted further leaching tests at CENIM and microprobe analysis at the Universidad Complutense. The processed data can be retrieved in [1].

WEEE and Low-Carbon Technology Waste Assessment

The available quantity of materials contained in WEEE and low carbon technologies is based on a previous research [2], where domestic material requirements for technologies supporting Spain's energy and digital transition until 2050, aligning with national policies was analyzed. Using a dynamic Material Flow Analysis (MFA) in MATLAB, we retrospectively (1990–2022) and prospectively (2023–2050) assessed the flows of ten critical metal groups within the system boundary of technology installation and

end-of-life. Eight key technologies, categorized by MFA approach were assessed: Wind, photovoltaics, electric vehicles, electrolyzers, energy storage batteries, charging stations, power lines, substations, and electronic equipment. Additionally, end-of-life internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles were considered as a recycling source. The selected metal groups—including aluminum, copper, cobalt, lithium, nickel, and rare earths—were chosen based on their role in mining concessions, technological demand, and EU classification as critical or strategic materials. The resulting MFA responds to what we call a transition scenario in which the objectives of public policies related to energy and digital transition are achieved, accompanied by ambitious collection and potential recycling rates by 2050. The generated data can be retrieved in [2].

Exergy replacement cost methodology

Based on the mass quantifications from WEEE and mining waste assessments, an exergy-based evaluation was conducted to determine the thermodynamic availability of critical materials in secondary resources in Spain.

Particularly, the *Exergy Replacement Costs (ERC)* methodology developed by Valero and Valero [3] was used. This method provides a fundamental framework for assessing energy and material resource use. This is because exergy incorporates key physical characteristics that determine a mineral's value, including composition, concentration, and cohesion degree. By introducing *exergy costs*, this methodology also accounts for the energy required to extract, concentrate, and refine commodities. The *exergy replacement costs* are defined as the total exergy needed to extract and concentrate minerals from a fully dispersed state (modeled as Thanatia [4], a theoretical resource-depleted Earth) using current technology. Hence, the rarer and harder a mineral is to extract and refine, the greater its exergy replacement cost. This metric allows for the evaluation of a mineral's *physical criticality*, measured in energy units like kJ or ktoe. Exergy replacement cost values for the elements can be retrieved in [4] and are expressed in kJ/kg. Accordingly, an exergy assessment was performed to quantify the thermodynamic value of the mineral capital contained in the analyzed mining waste and WEEE available in Spain. The ERC of a given technology or mining site is then calculated as:

$$ERC = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \cdot ERC_i \quad (Eq. 2)$$

Where m_i is the sum of each element contained in the given technology or mine site and ERC_i the corresponding exergy replacement cost of the particular element.

3. Results

Figure 1 presents a Sankey diagram illustrating the exergy flows of bulk metals (Al, Cu, Ni, and Mn) recoverable from secondary sources (i.e., end-of-life devices and mine tailings). These flows are calculated based on the Exergy Replacement Cost (ERC) of each metal and their respective masses.

When analyzing the recovered and lost fractions from end-of-life equipment, it is observed that approximately 53% of the materials' exergy is recovered, while the remaining 47% is lost during collection or recycling. Most of this exergy originates from aluminum (primarily from passenger cars), with a smaller contribution from copper.

Including the materials available in mine tailings increases the recovered exergy fourfold, mainly due to the presence of aluminum. However, it is important to note that most aluminum in tailings exists in the form of alumina. While alumina has industrial applications, it is not a source of metallic aluminum, so this information should be interpreted with caution.

Figure 2 shows the Sankey diagram for the exergy flows of tech metals (Co, Ag, Au, Nd, Dy, Pt, Pd and Li). In this case, losses are greater than those for bulk metals, primarily because these materials are present in much lower concentrations, making both collection and recycling more challenging.

More than 58% of the exergy (measured by ERC) from end-of-life devices is lost, with only 42% recovered through recycling. Over 60% of the recovered exergy comes from cobalt, while 16% is from palladium or platinum. When all secondary sources are considered—including mine tailings—the recovered exergy fraction can increase to 46%, mainly due to the significant presence of cobalt and silver in mine waste. The corresponding exergy values of mining waste and technological metals are available in [5] and [6], respectively.

Compared to the exergy of metals embodied in the analysed products predicted to be consumed in Spain in 2025, the aluminium from secondary sources could represent up to a 136 % of the exergy demanded by aluminium. Again, it must be reminded that aluminium in mine wastes is in the form of alumina. Besides, it would not be real to compare the complete stock in tailings with annual flows, since it does not seem feasible to extract all of the resource over one year. If a 20-year exploitation of the tailings is assumed (with constant production), 48 % of the demand of aluminium could be met with secondary sources. Under the same assumption, 30 % of the demand of silver (exergy based) for 2025 could be covered with secondary sources, more than one third of that fraction coming from tailings..

Exergy Replacement Cost (ERC) [TJ]

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Figure 1. Sankey diagram of exergy flow of bulk metals in Spanish economy in 2024.

Exergy Replacement Cost (ERC) [TJ]

Exergy Replacement Cost (ERC) [TJ]

Figure 2. Sankey diagram of exergy flow of tech metals in Spanish economy in 2024.

4. Conclusions

The increasing global demand for raw materials, particularly in the context of the ecological transition, underscores the need for sustainable resource management. As renewable energy technologies expand, reliance on critical minerals will intensify, making the assessment of secondary resource recovery essential. This study applied exergy replacement cost (ERC) analysis to evaluate the feasibility of recovering key metals from mining waste and end-of-life technological devices (WEEE) in Spain. The results highlight significant differences in the recovery potential of bulk and tech metals. While approximately 53% of the exergy content in bulk metals can be recovered, the figure drops to 42% for tech metals, primarily due to their lower concentrations and higher recycling complexity. However, incorporating secondary sources like mine tailings can increase recovery rates, particularly for cobalt and silver. Despite these opportunities, significant thermodynamic and technological challenges remain. Many materials, especially those found in mine tailings, exist in non-metallic forms that are difficult to process. Furthermore, losses during collection and recycling continue to pose obstacles to achieving a circular economy.

The findings underscore the importance of exergy-based assessments in resource sustainability strategies. By quantifying the thermodynamic limitations of material recovery, this approach provides a realistic perspective on the feasibility of secondary mining. Future efforts should focus on improving recycling technologies, optimizing resource recovery processes, and developing policies that promote efficient material use.

5. References

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6. Acknowledgment

This research was funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, and FEDER (EU) under grant agreement PID2023-148401OB-I00 and PID2020-116851RB-I00